

Different Kernel Colour Maize Vulnerability to *Sitophilus zeamays* Storage Insect Pest

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Abstract

*Maize kernels with various colours possess nutritional and sometimes pest resistance benefits. A study was conducted in Morogoro, Tanzania, to investigate farmer's claim that he was planting some red kernelled maize, which is very rare in Tanzania because red kernels were resistant to storage insect pests. Dark red and typical red cobs were purchased from the farmer and planted and subsequently a storage experiment was conducted to test the farmer's hypothesis. The red, dark red, deep yellow, yellow, light yellow, orange and white kernels were put in polyethylene bags and infested with *Sitophilus zeamais* then stored under normal room conditions alongside an insecticide treated control sample. Vulnerability to the storage insect pest varied among the different colours. Orange kernels were least vulnerable; light yellow and red kernels also possessed some level of resistance while dark red kernels were most vulnerable. Colour based resistance observed, however, did not show expected linearity according to the concentration of kernel colour determining biochemicals: carotenoids and anthocyanins. It was therefore concluded that attributes other than colour were also responsible for the observed variability in resistance, either concurrently independently or interacting with the kernel colours. More study of the association of maize kernel characteristics and kernel colour with storage insect pest vulnerability in relation to genotypes of the crop seems to be worthwhile.*

Keywords:

Pigmented corn, Anthocyanins, Germination, Seedling weight, Resistance mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

Maize is the world's most-produced food crop (Wernick, 2018, Statista, 2018). Currently, production worldwide is estimated to be slightly exceeding 1,000 million metric tons (USDA, 2018), well above any other cereal. Believed to have originated in South Central Mexico as a domesticated derivative of the wild Mexican grass teosinte *Zea mays ssp. parviglumis* (Buckler and Stevens, 2005), the crop (*Zea mays* L. *ssp mays*) is an extensively diverse cereal. Diversity in the crop appears in numerous plant, ear, kernel as well as phenological characteristics (Perales *et al.* 2005; van Etten *et al.* 2007; Alercia 2011). Various different descriptors including those of CIMMYT, IBPGR, and UPOV are quoted (Alercia *et al.* 2011) for the characterization and evaluation of maize genetic resources. Kernel characteristics including kernel type and kernel colour are an extremely important distinguishing descriptor of the crop. Kernel types, described as dent, flint, pop, flour, sweet and waxy are based mainly on texture in relation to the starch composition of the kernel. Dent kernels have a depression at the top (crown) of the kernel originating from differential drying of the hard and soft starch that composes the kernel. Accordingly (Encyclopaedia, 1999), flint corn has no such depression because it is composed of hard starch with very little soft starch, therefore, it dries uniformly with the crown becoming round. Likewise, popcorn is devoid of soft starch, and it is an extreme type of flint corn with small, hard kernels; flour corn is soft because it is composed largely of soft starch; while sweet corn kernels do not allow conversion of sugar to starch as it is normal in other kernel types, and develop into wrinkled translucent seeds (*Ibid*). Waxy kernels are made of endosperm composed of solely or almost solely amylopectin (Li *et al.*, 2018; Yu *et al.* 2015; Wikipedia, 2014). Normal kernels contain on average 25% amylose and 75% amylopectin (Yu *et al.* 2015; Wu *et al.* 2006)

Kernel colour varies extensively in maize. This ranges from white, yellow, red, black; to orange (van Hoose, 2015; Stewart, 2015; Weidenbener, 2018), blue (Monica *et al.*, 2017; Nankar *et al.*, 2016; Ron-Parra *et al.*, 2016), pink (Covington, 2014), purple (Alercia, 2011; Nannas and Dawe, 2015; Navarro *et al.*, 2018), brown (Grobman *et al.*, 1961; Alercia, 2011; Gyori, 2017) and even bronze (Grobman *et al.*, 1961; Covington, 2014; Nannas and Dawe, 2015;), metallic silver (Gyori, 2017) and green (Grobman *et al.*, 1961; Covington, 2014; Annon, 2018). Maize cobs may have mixed kernel colours. Thus we also have the so-called "all-coloured corn" (Wikipedia, n.d.), "Mixed corn" (EAC, 2014)

and even “Rainbow corn” (Spector, 2016) varieties. The East Africa Community categorizes maize grains as “mixed” when different coloured grains exceed 5% of yellow or red grained maize, or exceeding 2% of white grains (EAC, 2014). Most commercial colours of maize are, however, white and yellow, with a predominance of yellow. Worldwide, about 90% of produced maize is yellow grain type (VIB, 2017). Most of the white maize produced globally (over 90%) is produced in developing countries (FAO and CIMMYT, 1997). Africa produces 90% of its maize as white maize (VIB, 2017).

Differences in the biochemical background are the reasons for the different kernel colours of maize. Two metabolic pathways are described to be responsible for kernel colour : carotenoid synthesis pathway that results into yellow kernels, and anthocyanin pathway responsible for red and purple kernel colours (Ford, 2000). Each pathway is under the control of a specific gene, and white kernels result from the absence of either gene, so no pigment synthesized (*Ibid*). Blue, pink (Navaro *et al.* 2018) and black (Revilla *et al.* 2018, Lago *et al.*, 2015) colours of kernels are also anthocyanic. The differences in colour of anthocyanic kernels are attributed to differences in concentration of composing anthocyanic compounds. According to Navaro *et al.* (2018), blue corn has more

cyanidin type of anthocyanin; red corn has more perlagonidin while purple corn has more peonidin. Among the carotenogenic corn, on the other hand, yellow corn is accompanied by orange corn. Authors de Almeida Rios *et al.* (2014) have demonstrated that more intensity of the yellow color of kernels towards orange was responsible for the substantial increase (as much as 300%) of the α - and β -carotenes concentration.

Both carotenogenic and anthocyanic maize have nutritional benefits superior to white maize. Yellow and orange grains are sources of β -carotene the precursor of vitamin A very essential in human diet. Reasons, why white maize is preferred in Africa, are therefore without consideration of the health benefits. It has been argued that yellow corn is not popular in Africa because of being associated with food aid programmes thus perceived to be food for the poor and starving needy (James, 2010; Ranun *et al.*, 2014; VIB, 2017) and not a choice option. Another perceptual reason is that yellow corn is food that was intended to feed livestock in the US (James, 2010; VIB, 2017). That yellow maize is too sweet is another reason reported by VIB (2017). An attitudinal campaign based on nutritional contents will enable African people, the majority of whom consume maize as a staple, benefit from the nutritional superiority of carotenogenic and anthocyanic corn. While vitamin A is extensively known as an essential nutritional factor, perhaps more limited awareness is available about anthocyanins in nutrition. These substances are extremely important for the body as antioxidants and anti-inflammatory agents. They have been reported to have anti-cancer activity and also to be anti-obesity (Navarro *et al.*, 2018). In an experiment with carcinogenic cells, Monica *et al.* (2017) reported blue corn to be in possession of anti-cancer (cell anti-proliferation) activity. Anthocyanins have also been linked to reversing nervous system damage and also reversing effects of diabetes (Annon, 2016). Several authors have also reported anthocyanic maize kernels possessing higher contents of protein than white and yellow kernels (Annon, 2016; Sharing Gardens, 2017; Nankar *et al.*, 2016; Johnson and Jha, 1993) even though perhaps this may not be generalized as a ubiquitous observation.

There are various claims that pigmentation of maize kernels can provide or is accompanied by some defense mechanism against production environment limitations. In Mexico among farmers, Tuxill (n.d.) reports that yellow corn is esteemed for resistance to adverse conditions, both in the field and in stored grains. Wikipedia (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Blue_corn as of 25.10.2018) reports about Hopi blue corn varieties that are extremely tolerant to drought. Revilla *et al.* 2018 postulate possible defense functions of black kernels of maize against pests. Ron-Parra *et al.* (2016) also report that various pigments (other than white and yellow) are considered to be natural barriers of the maize kernels against invasion by pests and diseases. Compulsion and interest to conduct current research originate from observation in a farmer’s field in a locality in Morogoro during harvest that the farmer’s harvest was composed of numerous red cobs amongst a crop of white cobs. Wondering why red cobs while in Tanzania it is generally white maize that farmers had been growing, the farmer argued that red kernels were storing very well without attack by storage insect pests, and refused to give a cob free. After the purchase of a typical red and a dark red cob, subsequent years enjoyed a richness of colours from the red cobs alongside a stock of yellow kernelled population already in possession. An experiment was

subsequently designed to test the farmer's argument of red kernels possession of less vulnerability to storage insect pests.

Storage insect pests are a great nuisance to the handling of cereal and other harvested crop grains. As much as 30% or more of harvested crop grain is reported to be lost due to storage insect pests (Tefera *et al.*, 2016; Lopez-Castillo, 2018). In maize, post-harvest losses as a result of storage insects are estimated to range from 20 – 30% (Tefera *et al.*, 2011). The maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais*) is the commonest primary insect pest of stored maize in Tanzania. Farmers cannot usually tolerate this insect pest. If harvested maize grains are to be preserved for any considerable length of time the grains must be protected against the insect. Both effective methods of storage insect pests control available: chemical dressing and nowadays the use hermetic grain storage bags or hermetic metal or plastic containers such as barrels and drums, are expensive and not very affordable for resource poor farmers. Chemical dressing usually has to be repeated every 6 months, and the process of unloading and reloading the bags (usually woven polypropylene bags) is very laborious. Fumigation type of chemical insect pest control is least practiced by the farmer's majority of whom may not have proper facility that allows convenient fumigation, and because of the problem of re-infestation not long after preceding fumigation. Integrated and preventive control of storage insect pests is, therefore, the best way of curbing the insect's problem. Availability of plant genotypes with the ability to resist storage insect pests is, therefore, one of the most welcome opportunities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An experiment was designed involving 7 variants of maize based on kernel colour, to observe their vulnerability to the prevalent storage insect pest (*Sitophilus zeamais*) damage and loss of grain and seed value. The 7 variants were three yellow kernelled genotypes Deep yellow, Yellow, Light yellow; an orange kernelled genotype, white kernelled, and two red kernelled genotypes: Red and Dark Red. These kernel colour types were selected from a previous season nursery of coloured kernels maize crop harvest. A control was involved for the experiment, which was a storage insecticide dressed treatment. The crop for all variants used for the experiment was harvested at the same time after cobs were dry in the field in July as it is the usual time for harvesting maize in Morogoro. Harvested cobs were further dried under the sun for about two weeks then threshed by flailing. The threshed kernels were again exposed to solar radiation drying for about a week before the commencement of the experiment. About 1kg of each kernel colour type was then put in a transparent polyethylene bag for the experiment. Germination percentage change of the grains was considered a good indicator of internal damage of the kernels during storage, against insecticide treated control that would have no damage. Consideration was that once insect activity within the seed has reached a threshold level of damage the germ of the seed is totally destroyed (consumed) therefore no germination can occur. In maize usually, kernels whose germ or embryo have been consumed by insects are of little value and they disintegrate easily into flour, dust, and bran accompanied with secondary insect pest (moths) woven casts. Therefore, germination percentage of seeds for each kernel colour type as well as the insecticide treated control was tested at the beginning of the experiment by sowing the seeds in bowls with sand as a medium. Several other parameters thought to relate with kernel vulnerability to insect damage were also assessed. These were *Sitophilus* and later on moth insect counts in each stored sample, % number of kernels with insect holes, kernels with more than one hole, number of holes per kernel, number of live (*Sitophilus*) insects as well as seed and seedling vigour in terms of speed of germination and seedling weight respectively.

After sowing the seeds and wetting the medium to surface saturation with water, counting of germinated seeds (seedlings emerged protruding from below the soil surface) was counted after 72 hours from the time of sowing then every day to the 5th day then on 7th and 10th days, respectively. This was based on experience that by 5th day most of the maize seeds will have already germinated, under Morogoro conditions. Daily germination data recording enabled computing the speed of germination in terms of Mean Germination Time (MGT) which is the time taken for the seeds to reach the median of germination record for the sample in the test. This computation is a measure of seed vigour. The weight of seedlings at the end of the germination period was also measured as an indication of seedling vigour.

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About 200g sub-sample was used for each sample of kernel colour type to measure kernel and insect parameters. A number of *Sitophilus* insects was therefore counted in each 200g sub-sample, as well as the other kernel and insect parameters. Data parameters were measured at the onset of the experiment then after one month, two months, 4 months, 6 months, 8 months and where applicable 10 months. Every time of data recording from the beginning of the experiment, live *Sitophilus* insects (actively walking) were introduced into the storage sample of the kernels, at a rate of 10 insects in each 300g of seeds. These insects were reared in a live insect (*Sitophilus*) nest in a polyethylene bag package of infested maize kept separately from the experiment samples. Germination test data were replicated (3 replications) to enable analysis of variance (Randomized Complete Block Design) and mean separation (Duncan's New Multiple Range Test). For the rest of the data, descriptive statistics were used to analyse the data, as well as correlation analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Germination capacity

Data on germination presented in Table 1 show variation in the ability of the stored grains to consolidate embryonic energy and grow into seedlings (germination). At the beginning of the storage experiment period, it is obvious from the Table that all grain colour types were sufficiently intact with almost equal capacity to resume growth and germinate. There was no statistically significant ($P \leq 0.05$) difference in germination capacity even though numerically the control (insecticide treated kernels) showed much less germination than the test kernels. It is most predictable that treating the control sample with insecticide suppressed germination considerably, perhaps through chemical injury or retardation of the germination process metabolism. Deep yellow and orange kernels were having the highest germination capacity of 95.6%, the insecticide treated control achieved germination of 73.3%.

One month after the beginning of storage the test samples still showed no significant variation in germination capacity. The control was no longer, however, the least in germination capacity. Instead the Dark red kernelled genotype began to be poorest inability to germinate. This genotype was already comparatively very low in germination after 2 months of storage, recording 67.8% against an experimental mean of 88.7% that includes the rest of the genotypes. Variation in germination after 2 months was statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) but this was obviously due to the dark red genotype. This genotype was alone significantly different from the rest of the genotypes and the control. After 4 months of storage, another genotype, the deep yellow, began to show a notable decline in germination, which by 6 months of storage it was also already very low (30%), second only to the lowest germination genotype, dark red kernelled.

Table 1. Percentage germination capacity changes of different kernel colour maize genotypes under the influence of storage insect pest attack

Kernel genotype	Initial	1 month	2 months	4 months	6 months	8 months	10 months
Deep yellow	95.6	97.8	94.4 b	72.2 b	30 b	0	0
Yellow	86.7	98.9	88.9 b	87.8 c	83.3 d	0	0
Light yellow	94.5	94.4	93.3 b	82.2 bc	42.2 b	44.4	0
Orange	95.6	91.1	94.4 b	82.2 bc	82.2 d	55.6	0
White	93.4	92.2	90 b	86.7 c	84.4 d	0	0
Red	86.7	88.9	87.8 b	83.3 bc	63.3 c	66.6	0
Dark red	85.6	83.3	67.8 a	47.8 a	7.8 a	0	0
Control	73.3	94.4	93.3 b	91.1 c	92.2 d	87.8	86
Mean	88.9	92.6	88.7	79.2	60.7	63.6 ¹	
S.E. \pm	10.84	5.3	4.81	7.04	8.23	12.57	
CV (%)	12.2	5.7	5.4	8.9	13.6	19.8	
Probability	0.255	0.055	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	25.11 ²	

¹ Mean, SE and CV computed only among those genotype where germination occurred. ² LSD_(0.05) value; compares only those four variants where germination occurred. Means followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different. Mean separation by DNMR at $P \leq 0.05$

Storing maize for as long as 6 months, according to this experiment, can be considered to be a period of time when vulnerability to storage insect pest damage can begin to be judged. Beyond 6 months the majority of the coloured kernels genotypes tested were already completely damaged, with no intact seed with the ability to germinate. Failure of seed to germinate, especially under insect damage threat, notably means the embryo is totally damaged, presumably by insect feeding activities. Sometimes internal feeding is extensive without obvious external observation. Many seeds that look normal from the external may yield very easily when pressed from the flat sides that touch each other during attachment to the peduncle. They yield easily because of empty space internally when the embryo and sometimes all the surrounding soft starch have been consumed leaving a thin and fragile outer cover. Such damaged seed is usually of very little remaining value, other than animal feed, for example. After 8 months of storage, however, three of the coloured kernel genotypes: Light yellow, Orange, and Red were still possessing the capacity to germinate which means those seeds germinating were intact with even the embryo not totally damaged.

Based on being the only ones germinating after 8 months like the insecticide dressed control, we can consider the genotypes light yellow, orange and red to have inherent ability to counteract storage insect pests particularly *Sitophilus* damage. This could be because of their colours, but it could as well be due to different genetic traits. At the same time, we can say that Dark red genotype was most vulnerable to storage insects damage, losing significantly in germination as early as 2 months after the beginning of storage. Next most vulnerable was deep yellow, where germination capacity was already as low as 30% when the kernels had been stored for 6 months.

If we can say that kernel colour determined comparative ability to resist storage insect pests damage, one thing that the data may not explain sufficiently is about the linearity of the colour influence on the prolongation of the kernel intactness in store against storage insect pests. Light yellow and orange showing better storability while yellow was vulnerable are not linear, because carotenoid concentration would increase from light yellow to yellow to orange, then vulnerability would presumably follow the same trend. Again, relating anthocyanin concentration with vulnerability, dark red would perhaps be less vulnerable because of higher concentration of anthocyanin in comparison to red, but the opposite was true. And if a high concentration is reason for more vulnerability, then red would not be better than white. One thing that was not also recorded about the kernels, anyway, was whether they were dent or flint. There seems to be an additional attribute responsible for the more prolonged storability of the light yellow, orange, and red kernels, rather than colour alone.

Vigour parameters

Mean germination time (MGT) and seedlings weight representing vigour of seeds and seedlings are presented in Table 2. Variation in MGT according to the analysis of variance ($P \leq 0.05$) was generally not existing among the tested materials for the whole period of 6 months when seeds of all samples were germinating. This includes the insecticide treated sample. Insect damage, therefore, even if present (at variable levels), could not influence the quickness or slowness of germination significantly. Seedling weight, on the contrary, showed significant variability among the kernel colour genotypes, at the beginning and after 4 months of storage. Four months after the beginning of storage, seedling weight was comparatively very low for the dark red genotype. This is the same one that showed the poorest germination after 4 and 6 months of storage.

Table 2. Seed (MGT) and seedling (g/seedling) vigour of different kernel coloured maize genotypes under storage insect pest influence

Kernel

Mean Germination Time (MGT, days)

Germinated seedlings fresh weight (g/seedling)

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genotype	Initial	1 month	2 months	4 months	6 months	Initial	4 months	6 months
Deep yellow	3.72	3.28	3.35	3.28	4.09	2.25 bc	2.47 b	2.08
Yellow	4.52	3.3	3.24	3.06	3.46	2.34 c	2.49 b	2.23
Light yellow	4.39	3.15	3.16	3.24	3.75	2.15 abc	2.51 b	1.32
Orange	3.85	3.37	3.21	3.19	3.87	2.35 c	2.55 b	2.33
White	4.34	3.58	3.27	3.35	3.56	1.7 a	2.27 b	2.19
Red	4.93	3.31	3.23	3.29	3.59	1.86 ab	2.0 b	2.47
Dark red	4.81	3.44	3.53	3.47	3.64	1.81 ab	0.78 a	1.6
Control	4.35	3.44	3.36	3.66	3.23	1.84	2.31 b	2.28
Mean	4.36	3.359	3.292	3.32	3.65	2.04	2.17	2.06
S.E. \pm	0.607	0.14	0.215	0.33	0.56	0.247	0.305	0.694
CV (%)	13.9	4.2	6.5	9.9	15.2	5.2	14.0	33.7
Probability	0.272	0.068	0.537	0.514	0.699	0.025	<0.001	0.492

Means bearing the same letter in a column are not significantly different. Mean separation by DNMRT at 0.05 level

Insect and kernel parameters

Figures 1 – 5 present observed insect and kernel parameters of the stored maize over the storage period, in relation to probable variability in insect damage vulnerability. In terms of *Sitophilus zeamais* insect counts, number of live insects, percent kernels with insect holes as well as number of kernels with more than 1 hole (Fig 1, 2, 3, 4) it is interesting to note that the orange kernel genotype was consistently promising, showing being least affected or in hosting the insects (*Sitophilus*). In Figure 5, it was also one of the genotypes hosting the least number of months from the beginning of the experiment to 6 months of storage. The orange kernelled genotype was also one of those three genotypes with intact, germinable grains beyond 6 months of storage. It is also interesting to note that the dark red genotype that showed the highest number of *Sitophilus* including the insect live adults (Fig 1 and 2 respectively) was having highest percentages of kernels with insect holes during storage (Fig 3) and almost highest number of kernels with more than one hole. This genotype evidently proved to be most vulnerable, even though in terms of moth insects (Fig 5) it hosted least numbers of the insect at 6 and 8 months of storage.

Fig 1. *Sitophilus* counts in different kernel colour maize

Fig 2. Live insect (*Sitophilus*) counts

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Fig 3. Percent kernels with insect holes

Fig 4. Number of kernels with > 1 hole

Fig 5. Moth counts invariably coloured maize kernels over 8 months storage period

Correlations

Correlations amongst insect, kernel, germination and vigour parameters of the stored seeds under the influence of insect damage are presented in Tables 3 and 4. Significant positive and negative correlations were observed amongst various parameters at different storage periods. Significant positive correlations ($P \leq 0.05$) existed between insect counts (Table 3) and a number of kernels with insect holes. This means that increasing number of insects increased a number of kernels with holes and therefore directly the holes were indeed made by the insects. Significant correlations between insect counts or percent number of kernels with insect holes and respectively 100 kernel weight, germination capacity as well as seedling weight parameters were negative. This means that increasing numbers of insects or kernels with the insect holes reduced kernel weight, germination, and vigour in terms of seedling weight (vigorousness of seedlings). Vigour in terms of MGT was generally not influenced significantly by insect counts or number of kernels with holes, with minor exceptions. Highly significant negative correlations ($P \leq 0.01$) were the associations between insect counts 4, 6 and 8 months of storage and 100 kernel weight 6 and 8 months of storage ($r > -0.88$ in the negative direction); between kernels with holes 4, 6 and 8 months and 100 kernel weight 6 months, and 8 months for percent kernels with holes 8 months of storage. It was also highly significantly negative for several other insect or insect holes parameters with kernel weight and seedling weight. Initial germination (maximum; terminating the germination test data recording after 10 days of incubation) and early 72hrs germination after one month of storage were having no significant correlation with the kernel or insect parameters. Amongst germination and seedling weight parameters all significant correlations were positive (Table 4) while with MGT they were negative. Decreasing

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MGT means increasing seed vigour. Therefore, higher vigour was also associated with higher germination capacity and higher seedling weight for those incidences where germination and seedling weight parameters were negatively correlated with MGT.

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Table 3. Insect and kernel parameters correlations amongst themselves and with germination and vigour parameters of seeds under influence of storage insect pest damage

Correlation parameters	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	
1 Insect count_Initial	-																		
2 Insect count 1 month	0.503	-																	
3 Insect count 2 months	0.221	0.74	-																
4 Insect count 4 months	0.197	0.665	0.83	-															
5 Insect count 6 months	0.164	0.716	0.857	0.959	-														
6 Insect count 8 months	0.189	0.777	0.925	0.95	0.928	-													
7 Krnls with holes_Initial	0.832	0.668	0.49	0.307	0.387	0.39													
8 Krnls with holes 1month	0.721	0.891	0.727	0.627	0.599	0.738	0.751	-											
9 With holes 2 months	0.495	0.858	0.852	0.764	0.746	0.814	0.555	0.84	-										
10 With holes 4 months	0.383	0.583	0.683	0.917	0.811	0.809	0.27	0.644	0.78	-									
11 With holes 6 months	0.297	0.63	0.89	0.952	0.94	0.902	0.424	0.64	0.812	0.893	-								
12 With holes 8 months	0.206	0.76	0.644	0.893	0.892	0.86	0.34	0.622	0.634	0.769	0.754	-							
13 100 kernel wght_Initial	-0.834	-0.75	-0.437	-0.5	-0.456	-0.528	-0.832	-0.83	-0.642	-0.535	-0.475	-0.596	-						
14 100 kernel wght 1month	-0.789	-0.632	-0.47	-0.662	-0.644	-0.568	-0.757	-0.713	-0.612	-0.718	-0.682	-0.685	0.871	-					
15 100kernel wght 2months	-0.574	-0.81	-0.454	-0.579	-0.508	-0.631	-0.59	-0.781	-0.668	-0.567	-0.451	-0.73	0.909	0.707	-				
16 100kernel wght 4months	-0.702	-0.687	-0.583	-0.733	-0.597	-0.712	-0.58	-0.841	-0.762	-0.833	-0.694	-0.682	0.872	0.834	0.848	-			
17 100kernel wght 6months	-0.403	-0.771	-0.815	-0.929	-0.892	-0.924	-0.45	-0.814	-0.789	-0.897	-0.893	-0.872	0.61	0.728	0.634	0.804	-		
18 100kernel wght 8months	-0.198	-0.708	-0.768	-0.934	-0.883	-0.947	-0.347	-0.686	-0.66	-0.799	-0.818	-0.933	0.588	0.636	0.704	0.753	0.918	-	
19 Initial germination 10dys	0.396	0.482	-0.069	0.177	0.159	0.091	0.225	0.284	0.391	0.307	0.071	0.397	-0.529	-0.44	-0.638	-0.411	-0.167	-0.141	
20 Germinn 1 month 72hrs	0.276	0.112	-0.274	-0.005	-0.014	-0.082	-0.012	0.188	-0.133	0.15	-0.103	0.233	-0.128	-0.25	-0.099	-0.133	-0.253	-0.087	
21 Germinn 1 month 96hrs	-0.243	-0.4	-0.866	-0.663	-0.618	-0.711	-0.366	-0.551	-0.727	-0.636	-0.811	-0.299	0.272	0.354	0.189	0.523	0.624	0.52	
22 Germinn 1 month 10dys	0.087	-0.507	-0.849	-0.618	-0.591	-0.752	-0.178	-0.454	-0.715	-0.462	-0.649	-0.379	0.193	0.083	0.331	0.383	0.493	0.557	
23 Germinn 2months 72 hrs	-0.096	-0.219	-0.791	-0.54	-0.534	-0.592	-0.277	-0.379	-0.533	-0.469	-0.718	-0.157	0.066	0.204	-0.055	0.302	0.498	0.397	
24 Germinn 2months 96 hrs	-0.353	-0.531	-0.901	-0.782	-0.739	-0.828	-0.539	-0.668	-0.737	-0.695	-0.874	-0.514	0.509	0.569	0.426	0.683	0.745	0.721	
25 Germinn 2months 10dys	-0.357	-0.497	-0.886	-0.761	-0.695	-0.807	-0.482	-0.674	-0.74	-0.716	-0.859	-0.464	0.466	0.526	0.384	0.689	0.748	0.691	
26 Germinn 4months 72 hrs	0.276	-0.035	-0.605	-0.649	-0.585	-0.614	0.046	-0.059	-0.286	-0.474	-0.656	-0.373	0.002	0.151	0.058	0.27	0.412	0.576	
27 Germinn 4months 96 hrs	0.142	-0.235	-0.743	-0.833	-0.762	-0.768	0.046	-0.275	-0.525	-0.757	-0.85	-0.537	0.044	0.283	0.108	0.425	0.686	0.692	
28 Germinn 4months 10dys	-0.23	-0.545	-0.82	-0.954	-0.89	-0.872	-0.266	-0.567	-0.789	-0.945	-0.974	-0.731	0.414	0.624	0.438	0.712	0.865	0.802	
29 Germinn 6months 72 hrs	-0.182	-0.716	-0.635	-0.866	-0.807	-0.8	-0.152	-0.577	-0.8	-0.877	-0.764	-0.849	0.478	0.554	0.664	0.697	0.8	0.775	
30 Germinn 6months 96 hrs	-0.223	-0.701	-0.726	-0.968	-0.946	-0.895	-0.29	-0.621	-0.717	-0.906	-0.887	-0.953	0.517	0.699	0.61	0.713	0.935	0.918	
31 Germinn 6months 10dys	-0.192	-0.626	-0.684	-0.966	-0.921	-0.875	-0.232	-0.574	-0.656	-0.912	-0.873	-0.939	0.486	0.686	0.579	0.712	0.924	0.923	
32 MGT_Initial	0.235	0.44	0.621	0.266	0.284	0.51	0.531	0.603	0.341	0.08	0.314	0.191	-0.361	-0.16	-0.296	-0.319	-0.405	-0.441	
33 MGT 1 month	-0.082	-0.326	0.09	-0.106	-0.125	-0.112	0.082	-0.273	-0.019	-0.163	0.049	-0.388	0.093	0.118	0.21	0.108	0.342	0.232	
34 MGT 2 months	-0.047	-0.017	0.581	0.638	0.602	0.526	0.072	0.09	0.313	0.573	0.748	0.295	-0.001	-0.32	0.101	-0.284	-0.467	-0.459	
35 MGT 4 months	-0.704	-0.432	0.162	0.16	0.126	0.154	-0.461	-0.441	-0.268	-0.057	0.139	-0.049	0.499	0.388	0.397	0.286	0.086	-0.15	
36 MGT 6 months	0.14	0.445	0.087	0.419	0.451	0.259	0.028	0.17	0.409	0.494	0.324	0.576	-0.279	-0.43	-0.413	-0.294	-0.35	-0.285	
37 Seedlings weight_Initial	0.333	0.18	-0.322	-0.095	-0.099	-0.219	-0.04	0.102	0.128	0.174	-0.134	0.081	-0.139	-0.2	-0.159	-0.118	-0.039	0.187	
38 Weight/seedling_Initial	0.329	0.08	-0.332	-0.161	-0.161	-0.275	-0.07	0.085	0.05	0.128	-0.157	-0.037	-0.021	-0.13	0.019	-0.038	-0.031	0.26	
39 Seedlings wght 4months	-0.162	-0.579	-0.949	-0.903	-0.888	-0.922	-0.386	-0.601	-0.765	-0.772	-0.953	-0.667	0.394	0.521	0.397	0.613	0.82	0.812	
40 Wght/seedling 4months	-0.146	-0.457	-0.912	-0.795	-0.751	-0.843	-0.357	-0.555	-0.691	-0.677	-0.87	-0.5	0.335	0.415	0.313	0.572	0.717	0.72	
41 Seedlings wght 6months	-0.187	-0.553	-0.549	-0.913	-0.85	-0.79	-0.166	-0.502	-0.56	-0.888	-0.789	-0.929	0.48	0.689	0.584	0.7	0.87	0.885	
42 Wght/seedling 6months	-0.154	-0.308	-0.244	-0.602	-0.391	-0.547	0.063	-0.432	-0.315	-0.678	-0.398	-0.633	0.433	0.41	0.61	0.715	0.627	0.718	

Bold numbers = Significant at 0.05. If > 0.875, significant at 0.01.

Number of observations: 8

Table 4. Correlations amongst germination and vigour parameters of variously coloured maize under the influence of storage insect pests

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Correlation parameters	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42		
1 Initial Germinn																									4	
9 (10days)	-																								2	
2 Germinn 1 month	0.222																									
0 72hrs	9	-																								
2 Germinn 1 month	0.285	0.425																								
1 96hrs	2	4	-																							
2 Germinn 1 month	0.112	0.633																								
2 10days	2	5	0.808	-																						
2 Germinn 2months	0.521	0.438		0.723																						
3 72hrs	1	6	0.958	6	-																					
2 Germinn 2months	0.193	0.359	0.932	0.766	0.866																					
4 96hrs	9	8	7	8	2	-																				
2 Germinn 2months	0.226	0.314	0.958	0.761	0.890	0.989																				
5 10days	8	3	2	6	4	2	-																			
2 Germinn 4months		0.560	0.689	0.683	0.712	0.737	0.709																			
6 72hrs	0.398	2	1	4	1	1	7	-																		
2 Germinn 4months	0.263	0.247	0.794		0.777	0.774	0.790	0.873																		
7 96hrs	1	1	8	0.685	6	8	1	1	-																	
2 Germinn 4months	-	0.103	0.790	0.646		0.826	0.828	0.684	0.895																	
8 10dys	0.117	7	6	5	0.675	3	8	4	4	-																
2 Germinn 6months	-	-	0.417	0.518	0.211	0.480	0.475	0.331	0.602	0.821																
9 72hrs	0.565	0.098	7	8	7	1	5	9	2	1	-															
3 Germinn 6months	-	-	0.487	0.448	0.355			0.474	0.715	0.886	0.900															
0 96hrs	0.312	0.204	7	5	8	0.627	0.604	1	4	5	1	-														
3 Germinn 6months	-	-	0.475	0.414	0.352	0.620	0.602	0.516	0.744	0.886	0.875	0.992														
1 10dys	0.263	0.222	2	2	3	8	6	3	3	9	1	9	-													
3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.051	-	-													
2 MGT_Initial	0.474	-0.2	0.545	0.532	0.568	-0.64	0.633	0.314	0.235	0.189	9	0.144	0.126	-												
3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.277	0.314	0.306	0.085												
3 MGT 1 month	0.278	0.904	0.386	0.371	0.425	0.331	0.293	-0.51	0.177	0.053	7	6	9	7	-											
3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.186												
4 MGT 2 months	0.416	0.358	-0.76	0.486	0.814	0.751	0.745	0.877	0.884	0.757	0.289	0.493	0.533	6	0.453	-										
3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.137	-	-	0.492												
5 MGT 4 months	0.681	-0.55	-0.29	0.388	0.436	0.275	0.257	-0.81	0.565	0.178	4	0.003	0.065	0.177	9	0.62	-									
3		0.314		0.058	0.329		0.148	0.171	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.09	0.45									
6 MGT 6 months	0.843	3	0.163	6	3	0.118	6	7	0.081	-0.37	0.732	0.573	0.533	0.594	0.396	9	1	-								
3																										
3 Seedlings	0.732	0.648	0.411	0.478	0.542	0.477		0.709	0.368	0.075	-	-	-	-	-	0.49	0.81	0.72								
7 weight_Initial	7	1	4	1	6	9	0.436	4	1	7	0.307	0.102	0.069	0.634	0.602	6	1	5	-							
3																										
3 Wght/seedling_In		0.741	0.355	0.538		0.469	0.401	0.731		0.112	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.77	0.55	0.956							
8 itial	0.512	3	9	9	0.431	1	6	6	0.345	3	0.169	0.028	0.004	0.548	0.652	0.44	7	4	9	-						
3																										
3 Seedlings wght	0.127	0.305	0.890	0.805	0.828	0.946			0.886	0.917	0.647	0.781	0.770	-	-	0.78	0.33	0.08	0.398	0.41						
9 4months	7	5	7	7	2	9	0.929	0.788	1	6	9	4	6	0.509	0.198	2	9	6	9	2	-					
4																										
4 Wght/seedling	0.284	0.416	0.945	0.838	0.903	0.974	0.970	0.828	0.869	0.842	0.495	0.628	0.628	-	-	0.80	0.43	0.13	0.540	0.52	0.969					
0 4months	9	4	6	5	8	8	8	9	5	2	8	7	4	0.607	0.336	3	1	3	8	4	9	-				
4																										
4 Seedlings wght	-	-	0.341	0.280	0.211	0.507	0.489	0.449	0.670	0.822	0.857	0.966	0.984	-	0.364	-	-	-	-	-	0.660	0.50	-			

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1	6months	0.332	0.311	5	7	3	3	2	4	7	5	7	0.009	2	0.46	0.02	0.58	0.151	0.07	1	9				
															5	9	6								
4	Wght/seedling	-	-	0.167	0.183	0.005	0.321	0.307	0.440	0.512	0.625	-	0.376	-	0.04	0.22	-	-	0.354	0.32	0.740				
2	6months	0.228	0.341	8	3	9	3	0.356	6	9	2	0.612	3	0.683	0.107	4	0.17	7	5	0.079	0.02	4	1	9	-

Bold numbers = Significant at 0.05. If > 0.875, significant at 0.01

Number of observations: 8

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The behavior of the data presented (insect, kernel, germination and vigour parameters with exception of MGT) and the correlations among parameters leave no doubt on the influence of the insect pests on a storage life of the seeds and different response or vulnerability of the variously coloured kernels. It is indeed encouraging that significant association of storage insect resistance, and kernel colour could be highlighted and the farmer's claim of colour based better storability of maize could not be totally refuted. It is important to note, however, that resistance based on colour may be just a component of resistance also caused by or originating from other different factors. Colour of maize kernels alone is determined by pigments located either in the pericarp, the aleurone surrounding the endosperm, or in the endosperm proper (Ron-Para *et al.*, 2016; Alercia, 2011; Floyd *et al.*, 1995; Wolf *et al.*, 1952). Those anatomical structural components of the seed (the embryo, in addition) may have various defense mechanisms against pests. In a study of two red kernelled genotypes (denoted C1 and C3) with yellow endosperms, Lopez-Castillo *et al.* (2018) found that endosperms of one genotype (C3) were the most susceptible while endosperms of the other genotype displayed the highest resistance to *Sitophilus zeamais*. This means that even though colours were the same (endosperm was inclusive of the aleurone), susceptibility was different indicating there are factors other than colour responsible for the difference in susceptibility of the two genotypes. Soujanya *et al.* (2016) attribute *Sitophilus* kernel resistance to biophysical, anatomical and biochemical traits in the kernels. Garcia-Lara and Bergvinson (2014) argued that major factors responsible for enhanced insect pest resistance are kernel hardness, pericarp proportion in the kernel; and also pointed out that increases in free phenolic acids in the endosperm were also associated with resistance. Lopez-Castillo *et al.* report previous documentation (Ayala-Soto *et al.*, 2014; Santiago *et al.*, 2013; Garcia-Lara *et al.*, 2007, 2004; Sen *et al.*, 1993; Arnason *et al.*, 1993) that cell wall components in the kernel impart resistance and that the principal cell wall components associated with storage insect resistance are soluble and cell wall phenolic acids, heteroxylans, hydroxyproline-rich glycoproteins and functional proteins such as peroxidases. Garcia-Lara *et al.* (2007) report that peroxidase activity, particularly, has been detected in the embryo and endosperm of insect resistant kernels. One of the peroxidase functions has been reported to be catalyzing cell wall reinforcement by diferulate (phenolic compound) cross-linking between hemicellulose molecules, increasing kernel hardness (Arnason *et al.*, 1992, 1993; Lopez-Castillo *et al.*, 2018). Apart from contributing to the structural strengthening of cell walls (in the pericarp) and kernel hardness, peroxidases according to Lopez-Castillo *et al.* (2018) also participate in the oxidation of soluble phenolic compounds in the aleurone layer as a biochemical defense against insect attack. Both the germ (*Ibid*) and the aleurone layer (Arnason *et al.*, 1993; Sen *et al.*, 1994; Ndolo *et al.*, 2013) contain phytochemical compounds deterrent to insects. Such deterrent compounds include soluble phenolic acids (coumaric and ferullic acids) and derivatives of those acids, such as phenolic acid amides and aromatic amines (*Ibid*). Phenolic acid amides, for example, have direct toxic effects on insects, suppressing insects neuron receptors (Arnason *et al.*, 1993; Fixon-Owoo *et al.*, 2003). Therefore, while kernel colour may perhaps have independent action against storage insect pests, it may as well act under combined effect with other biophysical (for example kernel hardness), anatomical (example pericarp thickness and proportionate volumes of endosperm and embryo) and biochemical factors. The effect may therefore not be direct or linear.

CONCLUSION

Results of this study have shown that farmer's claim of red maize kernel color based resistance to storage insect pests was indeed not in vain. There has been, however, a very pronounced deviation within the same red colour spectrum. Whereas typical red kernels showed notable resistance, dark red coloured kernels were most susceptible. Since red colour of maize kernels is caused by anthocyanins, and with assumption that dark red means a higher concentration of the anthocyanins, the observed results lack linearity. If anthocyanins are responsible for the resistance assumption is also that higher concentrations would not break the resistance. Instead they would increase the resistance. The observed higher vulnerability of the dark red kernels is therefore beyond expectation. Based on the observed results, there is a great probability that there were other attributes of kernels that were also responsible for the observed comparative resistance of red, orange and light yellow kernels against the vulnerability of the dark red and other colours. Those attributes may

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have acted independently or in interaction with the kernels colour. Those may be such attributes as the hardness of the kernels, pericarp thickness, various other physical attributes as well as biochemical attributes. There seems to be needed for more study of the association of maize kernel characteristics and kernel colour with storage insect pest vulnerability in relation to genotypes of the crop.

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